

Bosnia and Herzegovina's ERA Integration

Progress and recommendations

Progress

Internationalisation activities

- Proposal success rate in Horizon Europe almost on average of EU Member States
- Continuously rising participation in EUREKA and COST
- Signing of cooperation agreement with CERN, the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (2021)
- Over 53% of publications with international partners (2017–2021)

Research infrastructure activities

- Publication of Research Infrastructure Roadmap for Bosnia and Herzegovina by the Regional Cooperation Council (2022)
- Participation in DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) which is part of ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures)

Gender equality

- Eight public and five private universities have Gender Equality Plans
- 48 % female researchers (She Figures 2021)
- 47 % female grade A academic staff (She Figures 2021)

Research conditions

- Increased acceptance of Open Access by research community
- Increased number of Open Access publications to 60% in 2021
- Development of EURAXESS activities
- Award of Human Resources Excellence in Research Award logo for three public universities

Recommendations

Establish a comprehensive approach regarding R&I

- Update outdated science strategies
- Establish a state-level Research Infrastructure Roadmap to have an overview of the research landscape
- Speed up the Smart Specialisation Strategy process and consider extension to a Smart Specialisation Strategy for sustainable and inclusive growth

Further improve research conditions

- Increase investments in R&D to reach an R&D expenditure of 1% of gross domestic product in upcoming years
- Consider Responsible Research and Innovation elements as qualification and evaluation criteria in grant schemes
- Improve collaboration of academia with private sector to increase public-private co-publications

Increase international activities

- Launch science, technology and innovation internationalisation strategies to increase international cooperation
- Integrate the scientific diaspora in internationalisation activities
- Establish active participation in ERA meetings and engage in the new European Innovation Agenda

